

**STRUCTURE OF THE PERIODATES. PART III. MAGNETIC
STUDY OF THE PARAMAGNETIC PERIODATES
OF Cu, Ni, Co AND Y**

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The magnetic susceptibilities of the periodates of Cu, Ni, Co, Ce and Y have been determined. From the comparison of μ_B values of these ions with the theoretically calculated μ_B values, these periodates have been shown to be simple salts of the periodic acids and not the complex salts.

In previous communications (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 158 ; 1946, 23, 177) the diamagnetic susceptibility values of the periodic acid and the periodates of Na, Ag, Hg. and La were reported and their structures discussed. We have now determined the magnetic susceptibilities of the periodates of Cu, Ni, Co, Ce and Y, all of which are paramagnetic. As already pointed out (*loc. cit.*), it is not always possible to assign any definite formulae to the periodates from analytical results. These paramagnetic periodates can be represented by the simple salt as well as complex salt formulae. The magnetic susceptibility values of these periodates will definitely indicate the nature of the salts formed i.e. simple or complex ; because in the latter case, large deviations between the experimental and theoretically calculated values will occur.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Pure Analytical salts were used in the preparation of these periodates.

Copper periodate was prepared by the addition of $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ in dilute nitric acid to copper sulphate. (Found : Cu, 36.2 ; I, 36.3 ; O, 15.97. Cu_2HIO_6 requires Cu, 36.20 ; I, 36.17 ; O, 15.95 per cent) according to decomposition $4\text{Cu}_2\text{HIO}_6 \longrightarrow 8\text{CuO} + 2\text{I}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + 7\text{O}_2$.

Cobalt periodate was prepared by the action of KIO_4 on $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. (Found : Co, 25.97 ; I, 28.1 ; O, 12.22. $\text{Co}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{13} \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 25.87 ; I, 27.8 ; O, 12.36 per cent) according to decomposition $\text{Co}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{13} \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow 2\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{I}_2 + 12\text{H}_2\text{O} + 7\text{O}$.

Nickel periodate was prepared by the addition of $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ in dilute nitric acid to NiSO_4 . [Found : Ni, 31.2 ; I, 28.23 ; O, 11.75. $\text{Ni}_6(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 13\text{H}_2\text{O}$

requires Ni, 31.67; I, 27.50; O, 12.12 per cent] according to decomposition $Ni_3(IO_3)_2 \cdot 13H_2O \rightarrow 5NiO + I_2 + 13H_2O + 7O$.

Yttrium periodate was obtained as a white powder by adding $Na_2H_2IO_6$ in dilute HNO_3 to a solution of yttrium nitrate. (Found: Y, 24.15; I, 33.80; O, 15.2. $YIO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Y, 24.12; I, 34.54; O, 15.3 per cent) according to decomposition $YIO_3 \cdot 4H_2O \rightarrow Y_2O_3 + I_2 + 3H_2O + 7O$.

Cerium periodate was obtained as a yellow powder by the addition of $Na_2H_2IO_6$ in dilute HNO_3 to cerium nitrate solution. (Found: Ce, 33.4; I, 30.4; O, 11.50. $CeIO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$ requires Ce, 33.40; I, 30.2; O, 11.45 per cent) according to decomposition $2CeIO_3 \cdot 4H_2O \rightarrow 2CeO_2 + I_2 + 8H_2O + O_2$.

Susceptibility Determinations

The susceptibilities were determined by the modified Guoy's balance (Nevgi, *Current Sci.*, 1945, 4, 403). $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, freshly prepared and twice crystallised, was used as the reference substance. The working of the apparatus was checked by determining the magnetic susceptibilities of a number of specially purified paramagnetic salts. The experimental and reported values with % error for these are shown in Table I and susceptibility values for periodates in Table II.

TABLE I

No.	Substance.	Temp.	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$		% Error.
			Exp. (mean of 3 readings)	Reported.	
1.	$Fe(SO_4)(NH_4)_2SO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$	32.0°	31.2	31.1	0.30
2.	$KCr(SO_4)_2 \cdot 12H_2O$	33°	12.08	12.04	0.16
3.	$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$	32.6°	5.83	5.84	0.15

TABLE II

No.	Periodate.	Temp.	$\chi_M \times 10^{-6}$	
			(mean of 3 readings)	Per g. mo
1.	Copper periodate	32°	6.803	2387.85
2.	Nickel paraperiodate	32°	20.744	20108.24
3.	Cobalt diisoperiodate	32°	23.67	21887.0
4.	Tetrahydrated cerium mesoperiodate	32°	5.143	2155.58
5.	Tetrahydrated yttrium mesoperiodate	32°	9.072	3337.66

DISCUSSION

If it is assumed that the Curie's law is obeyed in the limited range of temperature used in the present investigation, the magnetic moment of the paramagnetic ions in the above periodates can be calculated in terms of Bohr magnetons according to the formula: effective magnetic moment in terms of Bohr magneton (μ_B) = $2.84 \times \sqrt{\chi_M \times T}$. The values of μ_B in the above periodates are calculated below. It is necessary to account for the diamagnetic contributions of the periodate ion and water molecules in these salts. The diamagnetic values of periodate ions have been calculated as shown in a previous paper (*ibid.*, 1946, 23, 177). The diamagnetic contributions of the cores of the paramagnetic ions have not been considered as these are too small to affect the result.

Calculations of Bohr magneton values for Co, Ni, Cu, Ce and Y in the periodates.

1. Cu in Cu_2HIO_6 .	
χ_M (periodate)	= 2387.65×10^{-6}
χ_M (IO_6 ion)	= -52×10^{-6}
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χ_M for 2 Cu^{++} ions	= 2439.65×10^{-6}
.. for Cu^{++} ion	= 1219.92×10^{-6}
μ_B for Cu	= $2.839 \sqrt{1219.92 \times 10^{-6} \times 306} = 17.8$
2. Ni ion in $\text{Ni}_2(\text{IO}_6)_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	
χ_M (periodate)	= 20163.24×10^{-6}
$2\chi_M$ (IO_6 ion)	= 104.40×10^{-6}
$12\chi_M$ (H_2O)	= -189.0×10^{-6}
$5\chi_M$ Ni^{++}	= $20,473.4 \times 10^{-6}$
χ_M Ni^{++}	= 4094.7×10^{-6}
μ_B Ni^{++}	= $2.839 \sqrt{4095 \times 10^{-6} \times 306} = 3.174$
3. Co ion in $\text{Co}_2\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	
χ_M (periodate)	= 21629.6
.. (I_2O_{11} ion)	= -101.4×10^{-6}
.. ($12\text{H}_2\text{O}$..)	= -189.0×10^{-6}
$4\chi_M$ (cobalt ion)	= 2185.7×10^{-6}
χ_M (cobalt ion)	= 5471.7×10^{-6}
μ_B for cobalt ion	= $2.839 \sqrt{5471.7 \times 10^{-6} \times 306} = 3.67$

In the above formula for periodate, cobalt ion has been given the valency of three. Cobaltic ion has got $\mu_B = 2$ (experimental), while the cobaltous ion has $\mu_B = 4-5$ (experimental). In the above periodate μ_B value for cobalt ion shows it to be in the cobaltous state. Therefore the formula of periodate is $\text{Co}_4\text{H}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and not $\text{Co}_4\text{I}_2\text{O}_{11} \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

μ_B for Y in $YIO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$		μ_B for Ce^{+++} in $CeIO_3 \cdot 4H_2O$	
χ_M (periodate) = 3337.66×10^{-6}		χ_M (periodate) = 2155.58×10^{-6}	
" IO_3 = -51.95×10^{-6}		" IO_3 = -51.95×10^{-6}	
$4\chi_M H_2O$ = -52.00×10^{-6}		$4\chi_M H_2O$ = -52.00×10^{-6}	
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χ_M (Y ion) = 3441.81×10^{-6}		χ_M Ce^{+++} = 2259.53×10^{-6}	
μ_B for Y ion = $2.839 \sqrt{3441.8 \times 10^{-6} \times 806}$		μ_B Ce^{+++} = $2.839 \sqrt{2259.53 \times 10^{-6} \times 806}$	
	= 2.909		= 2.356

The values of the effective magnetic moments calculated on the basis of the well known formulae of Hund, Van Vleck and Bose-Stoner are given in Table III along with the observed values of these ions in the case of these periodates.

TABLE III

Ion.	L.	S.	J.	Hund's formula $\sqrt{J(J+L)}$	Van Vleck formula $\sqrt{L(L+1) + 4S(S+1)}$	Bose-Stoner formula $\sqrt{4S(S+1)}$	Obs. magneton values in the periodate ^{ns} .
Cu^{++}	2	$\frac{1}{2}$	5/2	3.55	3.01	1.73	1.781
Ni^{++}	3	1	4	5.69	4.49	2.63	3.174
Co^{++}	3	$1\frac{1}{2}$	9/2	6.63	5.21	3.97	3.97
Ce^{+++}	3	$\frac{1}{2}$	5/2	2.54	*2.54	1.782	2.356
Y^{++}	2	$\frac{1}{2}$	3/2	2.677	3.0	1.732	2.909

*Calculated on the modified formula of Van Vleck.

The observed moments of Cu^{++} and Ni^{++} ions in their periodates show that in Cu , the quenching of the orbital moment is complete, while in Ni^{++} it is incomplete. The effective magnetic moment of Ni ion is intermediate between the calculated values on the Van Vleck and Bose-Stoner formulae. In the case of Co^{++} the magneton value is less than the calculated value from Bose-Stoner formula. This lower value is probably due to an internal magnetic field and it may not accord with the Curie's law. In the values obtained for Co^{++} by others there is the wide range of the P_{eff} experimentally found, the results being such that these values depart from the Bose-Stoner formula. Thus Chatillon (*Ann. Phys.*, 1928, 19, 187) has shown that P_{eff} for Co^{++} depends on the mode of preparation and the history of the material. In our case for periodate the value for Co^{++} comes to be lower than that recorded by others which possibly makes Co^{++} a special case for study and theoretical treatment. The value of P_{eff} in terms of μ_B for Co^{++} coincides with Hund's formula as expected from the rare earth ion. The moment determinations of the above periodates have shown that the values nearly coincide with those obtained from the theoretical formulae in the same way as the simple salts of other acids do. This shows that these periodates are the true salts of the periodic acids and not the complex salts. In the latter case large deviations between the experimental and theoretically calculated values would have occurred.